

Article

Digitization of vascular plant herbarium collections at the Central Siberian Botanical Garden, Novosibirsk, Russia

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Received: 25 September 2018 | Accepted by A.P.Dyachenko: 25 November 2018 | Published on line: 03 December 2018

Abstract

The herbaria at the Central Siberian Botanical Garden Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (CSBG) were started in 1946. There are two herbarium collections with their own codes and registrations in the Index Herbariorum: M.G.Popov Herbarium (NSK) and I.M.Krasnoborov Herbarium (NS). Approximately 800000 herbarium specimens of vascular plants, mosses, lichens and fungi collected in Siberia, the Russian Far East, Europe, Asia and North America are stored in NSK and NS. Digitization of the herbarium specimens of vascular plants at the resolution of 600 dpi began in 2014 using a special scanner, *Herbscan*, starting with type specimens. In 2017 a new research group Unique Scientific Unit – Herbarium (USU-Herbarium) was organized in the CSBG for the digitization and management of herbarium collections. Herbarium specimens are being digitized using three customized scanners: *Herbscan* and two *ObjectScan 1600*, according to the international standards, at 600 dpi, with a barcode, 24-color scale and spatial scale bar. Images and metadata are stored in the CSBG Database generated by *ScanWizard Botany* and *MiVapp Botany* software (*Microtek*, Taiwan).

Keywords: biodiversity, Central Siberian Botanical Garden, digitization, digital herbarium collections, vascular plants

Introduction

Botanical Science must adapt to the digital revolution and concede that information about plants should be available online. This process of virtualization of botanical sources, such as botanical publications and herbarium collections, is developing very quickly worldwide. Many herbaria have websites with their virtual collections available online, yet in Russia only a few institutions have such a facility, including the Central Siberian Botanical Garden (CSBG).

Herbarium collections are the most important source of scientific information on distribution of plants in the past and present, also allowing for simulations of future distribution dynamics. Only the herbarium sample reliably confirms the presence of the plant at a specific point of space and time. Herbarium collections and the data they hold are valuable for more traditional studies of taxonomy and systematics, but also for research in the

fields of ecology, bioengineering, conservation, food security, and ethnobotany (Kovtonyuk, 2015, 2017; Seregin, 2016, 2018; Kislov *et al.*, 2017; Kovtonyuk *et al.*, 2018; James *et al.*, 2018; NicLughadha *et al.*, 2018). The value and universality of herbarium specimens are recognized in most countries, where national and large regional herbaria are actively developing and improving. The herbaria at the CSBG were organized in 1946. There are two major herbarium collections with their own codes and registrations in the Index Herbariorum founded in CSBG: M.G.Popov's Herbarium (NSK) and I.M.Krasnoborov's Herbarium (NS) (Doronkin *et al.*, 2015). Nearly 800000 herbarium specimens of vascular plants, mosses, lichens and fungi collected in Siberia, the Russian Far East, Europe, Asia and North America are stored in NSK and NS (Fig.1).

Figure 1. (A) M.G.Popov Herbarium (NSK) and (B) I.M.Krasnoborov Herbarium (NS) in CSBG, Novosibirsk, Russia. Photo by N.Kovtonyuk

Materials and methods

Digitization of the vascular plants in the NSK and NS collections initially was undertaken with a customized *HerbScan* unit, which consisted of a flatbed scanner (*Epson Expression 10000XL*) modified for inverted use (Fig. 2). Currently digitization of samples is carried out using *Herbscan* and two *ObjectScan 1600* scanners. Each workstation consists of an *ObjectScan 1600* scanner, *ScanWizard_Botany* software (reg. number I41-018966) and *MiVapp_Botany* archive management system (reg. number I41-018969) software (*Microtek*, Taiwan). This integrated workstation is characterized by on-top scan design for full-frame focus, a maximum of 1600 dpi (equal to 1 Gigabyte pixels), color CCD, Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for specimen label and ID barcode, and image archive and privileged-account cloud management system. Specimens were scanned using international standards: with the resolution of 600 dpi, a barcode for each specimen, and a 24-color scale and scale

bar.

<http://www.snsb.info/SNSBInfoOpenWiki/attach/Attachments/JSTOR-Plants-Handbook.pdf>

Figure 2 depicts the stages of the scanning process. Upon scanning an herbarium specimen, the scan is stored in the connected PC. A barcode is attached to the specimen and stored electronically, using a barcode scanner. In addition to storage in the PC, the scanned image is copied to an external hard drive.

Figure 2. Scheme of the *HerbScan* system operation for scanning herbarium specimens

Following recommendations of the Global Plant Initiative (GPI), a training course *Specimen Digitization and Quality Assurance* was organized at Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew (London, UK) on 13–15 May, 2014 by Dr. Jonathan Krieger and his team. Dr. Nataliya Kovtonyuk attended this course and received a Certificate of Attendance (Fig. 3–4). This

Figure 3. Nataliya Kovtonyuk selects herbarium specimens for scanning. Photo by Irina Belyaeva

course was a prerequisite for starting digitization of the herbarium collections in the CSBG. Special emphasis was laid on providing online high-resolution (600 dpi) images and metadata for all type specimens (Kovtonyuk, 2015, 2017a) and creation of a “typo-theca,” a collection of type specimen images and copies of pertaining protologues (Fig. 5–6), as many protologues published in Russian have not been available in digital format. Images and metadata for 895 type specimens preserved at the NSK and NS are currently available on the *Virtual Herbaria* web site at the University of Vienna, Austria (<http://herbarium.univie.ac.at/database>) and some of them in JSTOR (<https://plants.jstor.org>).

The value of digital images of type specimens has recently grown, since it grants ready access to authentic material necessary for research and typification, thus providing for correct application of scientific names, as stated in Art. 7.1 of the International Code of

This is to certify that

Dr. Nataliya Kovtonyuk

has attended training in:

Specimen Digitisation and Quality Assurance

as a partner of the Global Plants Initiative Programme

held at the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, London, United Kingdom, on 13-15 May 2014

Dr. Jonathan Krieger
Global Plants Initiative
Project Coordinator
Herbarium, Library, Art and Archives
Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew

Dr. Eimear Nic Lughadha
Senior Responsible Owner,
Global Plants Initiative
Herbarium, Library, Art and Archives
Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew

Figure 4. Certificate of Attendance. Photo by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi, and Plants (ICN) (Turland *et al.*, 2018) and demonstrated in recent publications (Kovtonyuk and Belyaeva, 2015; Kuzovkina *et al.*, 2016a; Kuzovkina *et al.*, 2016b; Kovtonyuk, 2017b; Belyaeva *et al.*, 2018). Type specimens are kept in the CSBG

Figure 5. L.Lukmanova digitizes type specimens on *Herbscan*. Photo by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

Figure 6. Typo-theca in NSK. Photo by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

in designated cabinets for better preservation and control of handling.

A new research group *USU-Herbarium* was organized in the CSBG in 2017 (registered at ckp-rf.ru as ‘USU 440537’) with the purpose of digitization and management of herbarium specimens in the NS and NSK collections.

Figure 7. Workflow at the workstation *ObjectScan 1600*
(<http://www.microtek.com/products.php?KindID=12&ID=373>)

The digitization process is shown in Figs.7–9 and includes the following 6 steps:

1. Mounting of dry plant material onto an herbarium sheet;
2. Check of the identification and nomenclature by a specialist;
3. Barcoding the specimen: printing a barcode on the thermal printer and affixing it to the herbarium sheet;
4. Placing the herbarium sheet, 24-color scale and scale bar (Fig. 8a) on the scanner platform and image capturing;
5. Metadata generation, label OCR by *ScanWizard Botany* and verification of the label text by experts;
6. Archive management by *MiVapp-Botany*.

Figure 8. I.Deyun scans herbarium specimens of NSK collections using *ObjectScan* 1600. 8a. The scale bar. Photos by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

Figure 9. Evgeniya Gatilova scans herbarium specimens of the NS collections using *ObjectScan*1600. Photo by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

Specimen label information is recognized and automatically saved under herbarium code and specimen serial number in XML format through *ScanWizard-Botany*. *MiVapp-Botany* is a web-server system and a specimen image authentication database aiming for an efficient and integrated multi-functional platform. After hierarchical login-based image quality and metadata profile validation by experts (Fig. 10), *MiVapp-Botany* can quickly update the system and make verified specimens accessible for users.

Overview

Data on the employment of some type specimens stored in NSK in previous taxonomic research were published by Kovtonyuk and Belyaeva (2015) and Han (2016).

Currently about 15000 herbarium specimens from NS and NSK have been digitized at 600 dpi by special scanners *HerbScan* and *ObjectScan* and are available for researchers worldwide. Images and metadata of herbarium specimens are stored in the CSBG Database (<http://84.237.85.99:8081>), generated by *ScanWizard Botany* and *MiVapp Botany* (Kovtonyuk *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 10. Verification of herbarium specimens by expert Irina Han. Photo by Nataliya Kovtonyuk

The database is structured in such a way that, while using a specimen record, the user can access a high-resolution image along with the following information: specimen ID (= barcode), family name, scientific name (genus, species, author of taxon), collector's name and collection date and the country and administrative region. Alternatively, a query may be submitted using habitat characteristics as key words, for example, "pine forest"

("сосновый лес" in Russian), "meadows" ("заливные луга"), etc. Images of specimens, label data and maps are available for downloads (the latter as attached images) (Figs. 11–13).

CSBG SBRAS Language Register Login

Advanced Query

Institute Code

Collector

Locality

Collection Period Start Date to End Date

Specimen ID

Family

Genus

Scientific Name

Search

< Previous Page 1 Next Page > 12

	Thumbnail	Specimen ID	Family	Scientific Name	Collector	Collection Date
1		NS0011754	Salicaceae(Salicaceae)	Salix gordejvii Chang et Skvorts.	Семихов В., Скворцов А.К.	1977-08-09
2		NS0011755	Salicaceae(Salicaceae)	Salix gordejvii Chang et Skvorts.	Скворцов А.К.	1977-08-09

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Figure 11. Genus *Salix* in CSBG Digital Herbarium database

Specimen Image Label Data Attachment Image

Download the original image

Revised Records

Division	Tracheophyta (Tracheophyta)			
Class	Magnoliopsida (Magnoliopsida)			
Order	Malpighiales (Malpighiales)			
Family	Salicaceae (Salicaceae)			
Genus	Salix (Salix)			
Species	Salix caesia Vill. subsp. tschuenensis N.Bolschakov ()			
Scientific Name	Salix caesia Vill. subsp. tschuenensis N.Bolschakov			
Common Name				
Specimen ID	NS0000363			
Institute Code	None (Central Siberian Botanical Garden SB RAS)			
Category	Normal			
Status	Good			
Identification Date				
Identifier Name				
Collection Date	1933-07-14			
Collector	Конюхова Г., Шенникова Н., Зайтцева Л.			
Collection Number				
Country Code	RU (Russian Federation)			
Country Name	Россия			
Administrative Area	Республика Алтай			
Locality	Ойротский экотон, обл. Юго-восточный Алтай, Чуйская степь, Окр. Коу			
Longitude	88°37'16" E	Latitude	49°59'52" N	
Altitude		to		meter
Notes	Тиневой степь			

Figure 12. Example of a record in CSBG Digital Herbarium

The image shows a digital interface for a herbarium specimen record. On the left, a scanned label from the 'ГЕРБАРИЙ Западно-Сибирского филиала Академии Наук СССР' (Herbarium of the West Siberian Branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences) is displayed. The label contains handwritten text: 'Salix caesia Vill.', 'Salix caesia Vill. sbsp. tschujensis N. Bolschakov', '1990', and 'specimen authenticum'. Below this, it mentions 'ГЕРБАРИЙ им. П. Н. КРЫЛОВА ДУБЛЕТ при Томском Университете им. В. В. Куйбышева' and 'Salix minutiflora Turcz. Determin. М. Амброзия'. The collection details include 'Обросток в долине р. Чуя, Юго-восточный Алтай, Чульская степь Окр. Кош-Агач. Пойменный луг по р. Чуя. 14 VII. 1933 г. Г. Колоскова, Н. Шетнера и Л. Зайцева.' A map in the center shows the location in the Altai region of Russia. On the right, a metadata form contains the following information:

- Division: Tracheophyta (Tracheophyta)
- Class: Magnoliopsida (Magnoliopsida)
- Order: Malviales (Malviales)
- Family: Salicaceae (Salicaceae)
- Genus: Salix (Salix)
- Species: Salix caesia Vill. subsp. tschujensis N. Bolschakov ()
- Scientific Name: Salix caesia Vill. subsp. tschujensis N. Bolschakov
- Common Name: (empty)
- Specimen ID: NS0000363
- Institute Code: None (Central Siberian Botanical Garden SB RAS)
- Category: Normal
- Status: Good
- Identification Date: (empty)
- Identifier Name: (empty)
- Collection Date: 1933-07-14
- Collector: Колоскова Г., Шетнера Н., Зайцева Л.
- Collection Number: (empty)
- Country Code: RU (Russian Federation)
- Country Name: Russia
- Administrative Area: Респ. Алтай
- Locality: Обросток в долине р. Чуя, Юго-восточный Алтай, Чульская степь, Окр. Кош-Агач
- Longitude: 88°37'10" E
- Latitude: 40°50'52" N
- Altitude: (empty) to (empty) meter
- Notes: Типовой материал

Fig.13. Herbarium label, map and metadata for *Salix caesia* Vill. ssp. *tschujensis* N.Bolschakov (NS0000363)

In our internal database each image is provided with the following information: barcode, type status, genus name, species name, author's name, infraspecific name, family name, collector's name, field collection number, date (yyyy-mm-dd), country, administrative region, latitude (degrees and minutes), longitude (degrees and minutes), label text, name of identifier, annotation and accepted name in the *Catalogue of Life* (CoL) with a link to this database. Data from herbarium labels are entered in 26 fields in the Calc tables of the *LibreOffice* software package. Parsing information from herbarium labels allows the placement of queries, exporting electronic tables to other media, such as domestic bio-resource networks or international databases, GBIF resources (gbif.org) and processing statistical data (Kovtonyuk *et al.*, 2018b). The CSBG Herbarium taxonomic database is

compatible with the international resource, *Catalogue of Life* (<http://www.catalogueoflife.org>), where an updated list of taxa is published every month (Roskov *et al.*, 2017). Names used in the herbarium labels have been verified and updated in accordance with the *International Plant Name Index* and POWO (<http://powo.science.kew.org>).

By the time of the paper publication, scanning was fully completed for Primulaceae (5028 sheets) and partially for a number of other families: Cystopteridaceae (891), Athyriaceae (436), Amaryllidaceae (2551), Orchidaceae (750), Poaceae (632), Fabaceae (418), Boraginaceae (664) and Asteraceae (550). Ninety-two recent herbarium collections representing the genus *Salix*, mostly from the Northern Urals and Taimyr Peninsula have been submitted to the CSBG Herbarium for digitization by the collectors I.N.Pospelov and E.B.Pospelova.

Our plan at the CSBG is to continue with digitization of herbarium specimens of various families as requested by multiple experts. Developing virtual herbaria will not only facilitate the study and research on herbarium specimens, analysis of variability and distribution of taxa, of their composition in certain geographical regions, but also speed up regional projects, such as the long-awaited *Flora of Russia*, along with worldwide biodiversity projects.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Sergey Lukyanchikov (CSBG SB RAS) and *Microtek's* engineers for consultations, Lyalya Lukmanova, Svetlana Krasnikova and Irina Deyun for the technical support of our research; Dr. Yury Rostkov and Dr. Irina Belyaeva for their help and consultations. In 2014–2016 digitization was supported by the Andrew Mellon Foundation. This work was partially financially supported by the Russian Foundation for Basic Research (grant No 15-29-02429) and the base project VI.52.1.5. (state reg. AAAA-A17-117012610055-3). Anonymous reviewers and editors are gratefully acknowledged.

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